

The therapeutic hypothermia in patients in a state of sudden cardiac arrest

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Summary

Patients with cardiopulmonary arrest do not have much chance to restore proper functioning. After the restoration of spontaneous circulation in patients enter as soon as possible the appropriate treatment. One of the treatments for patients with a therapeutic hypothermia. Patients were introduced in a controlled hypothermia - a lower body temperature to 32-34 degrees Celsius. The aim was - based on a review of scientific reports and information gathered research - demonstration of neurological recovery in patients after the use of therapeutic hypothermia, a reduction in mortality, the use of therapy in pregnant women as well as efficacy of therapeutic hypothermia protocols. The goals have demonstrated the efficacy of therapeutic hypothermia, confirmed the improvement in neurological function in patients as well as the reduction of mortality. The use of the therapy in pregnancy has brought good results at the same time having no negative impact on the fetus. Therapeutic hypothermia protocols provide a lot of information about the therapy and the possibility of improving it - also in relation to emergency medicine.

Keywords: *therapeutic hypothermia, cardiac arrest, induction phase, low temperature*

Introduction

Sudden cardiac arrest (SCA) is always loaded with dramatic consequences. In the past, cardiac arrest was a death sentence, because there was no specialization such as emergency medicine. Not applicable rescue techniques resulted in the death of patients. Only in the last century began to develop in technique as well as the treatment of post-resuscitation, which was extremely important for the continued good functioning of patients. Despite the enormity of the new resuscitation techniques and treatment of cardiac arrest after the incident is still a small percentage of CPR and resuscitation is effective. Very helpful to turn out new methods and techniques that we use during resuscitation and post-resuscitation treatment. An example here might be the introduction of automatic defibrillation (AED), new resuscitation medicines (vasopressin), training in first aid [1], [2] Therapeutic Hypothermia is defined as the controlled lowering of body temperature, is used since it has a protective effect on the brain by preventing the effects of hypoxia. To

reduce neurological complications caused by cerebral ischemia after cardiac arrest, use moderate hypothermia (32 - 34 °C) for 12 - 24 hours [3], [4].

Cardiac arrest determines the sudden cessation of cardiovascular function. It leads to the death of subsequent clinical, respiratory arrest and irreversible cessation of the central nervous system. Cardiac arrest is the cessation of effective systolic heart [5], [6], [7].

The most common cause of sudden cardiac arrest are cardiovascular disease, especially those that were not previously recognized. Through epidemiological studies, we can distinguish the individual diseases and other factors that are responsible for the arrest [8], [9].

Sudden cardiac arrest is usually caused by coronary heart disease (79%). Another reason is cardiomyopathies, which represent 11% of all causes.

Other pathologies or lack of them together, represent 10%.

Diagram 1. Causes of cardiac arrest
 Origin: Own study based on: Adler J., Plantz S.: Medycyna ratunkowa. Elsevier Urban & Partner, Wrocław 2005

The stadium of hypothermia - Swiss classification

STADIUM	TEMP.	SYMPTOMS
Stadium I	35-32°C	conscious, muscle tremor
Stadium II	32-28°C	apathy, impaired speech, motor coordination, lack of muscle tremors
Stadium III	28-24°C	unconscious, cardiac arrhythmias, abnormal pulse rate and breathing
Stadium IV	<24°C	cardiac arrest
Stadium V	<13,7°C	death

Table 1. The stadium of hypothermia - Swiss classification.
 Origin: Own study based on:
<http://hipotermia.edu.pl/?site=podstrona&id=41> [dostęp: 14.04.2016]

Indications for use of therapeutic hypothermia

The patients after cardiac arrest in the mechanism:

- ventricular fibrillation
- pulseless ventricular tachycardia
- asystole
- distraction mechanical - electrical

The condition is also effective resuscitation and hemodynamic return the shares cheese, aware of the patient's Glasgow Coma Scale (GSC <8) [10], [11], [12].

Contraindications to the use of therapeutic hypothermia

- The patient complies with the command (GCS> 8 points)
- It's been more than 6-8 hours of cardiac arrest
- There is a life-threatening bleeding or infection
- Coagulopathy (not applicable to drugs p / platelet)
- recent (<14 days) traveled major surgery
- Suspicion of intracranial pathology
- Severe hemodynamic instability despite the infusion of vasopressors
- The terminal illness
- Pregnancy [10], [13].

Techniques for cooling the body

Perfect cooling system has not been developed yet. The ideal device would be one that quickly would decrease body temperature cools preferentially target organs, and could be used during cardiopulmonary resuscitation - breathing. The temperature used for the HT, which has a positive effect and increases the complications of cardiac arrest in the range 32 ° C - 34 ° C [15], [16].

The technique of cooling the body is extremely important to use a to complex procedures with a view to increasing the effectiveness of therapy. Techniques for cooling the body can be divided into invasive and non-invasive.

The advantage of non-invasive techniques is the low cost and ease of use so that they can be used in the pre-hospital care. The disadvantage is a long time to achieve the target temperature (2 to 8 hours). Apart from the time disadvantage is the increased likelihood of chills, which badly affect the therapies [18].

The advantage invasive techniques is the speed of lowering body temperature. Unfortunately, these techniques are expensive and can be used only under strict supervision in a hospital. Top-tolerated by and cheap compared to the other was a cold infusion of intravenous fluids, the advantage is that the only invasive technique can be used in the pre-hospital. Infusion of 30 ml / hr kg of chilled Ringier's solution results in a temperature decrease of 2.5 - 3,3°C / h and is commonly used in combination with other methods of [13], [14].

Extracorporeal circulation

This method is used in transplants and open heart surgeries, but was also used in the treatment of therapeutic hypothermia. Because the blood is pumped through the body it can be used to change the temperature of the body. The cardiopulmonary bypass machine is mounted a heat exchanger through which blood can be cooled. It is a metal container having two circuits is in the first blood and in a second cooling fluid [13], [17].

Figure 1. Scheme of extracorporeal circulation
 Origin: Antoszewski Z., Gwóźdź B., Skalski J.: Hipotermia i hipertermia w zastosowaniu klinicznym. Wydawnictwo Śląsk, Katowice 2000, str. 290

It is a system that can temporarily replace the heart and lungs. The pump replaces the mechanical and the heart

pumps blood, it is cooled outside the body and returns into the body at a lower temperature to cool the patient. The oxygenator is replaced by the lungs, the air mixture is cooled and introduced into the patient [18], [19].

Figure 2. Operation of the machine for extracorporeal circulation. Origin: <http://www.jaimojeserce.eu/w-krazeniu-pozastrojowym.php> [dostęp: 20.04.2016]

The protocol conducting post-resuscitation hypothermia

When considering the use of a patient after cardiac arrest introduction of therapeutic hypothermia should take into account all the parameters of the patient, the method of cooling and any contraindications. Over time, the development of a therapeutic hypothermia began to form special protocols use this therapy to include all actions applied and the parameters of the patient. Depending on the clinical center carrying out the HT these protocols may vary. Polish Register of Therapeutic hypothermia under the auspices of prof. Janina Stępińska developed a specialized clinical protocols conducting therapeutic hypothermia [29]. You can highlight the treatment protocol using external and internal, also developed a special protocol for Air Rescue to be able to use terapię even in the prehospital phase. With these protocols, you can also collect data and create statistics that will enable the development of hypothermia treatment and better results of therapy for patients [20], [17]. Each protocol includes the following points:

- Patient Data
- Inclusion and exclusion criteria therapy
- The assessment of neurological patients
- The temperature output on admission
- treatment phase

Phases hypothermia

The induction phase

Prior to cooling the patient should always use sedation and relaxation. For sedation are the most common drugs such as Midazolamum, Propofolum, Fentanylum and Morphini Sulfas. It is important to relaxant drug came from a group

of not polarizing. The purpose of this phase is to obtain depending on your prior assumptions temperature between 34 ° C and 32 ° C, and that as soon as possible to return to the target temperature. The patient is connected to the monitoring device parameters and then the body temperature previously selected method. A simple and fast method to start cooling is intravenous fluid within the 1500 - 2000 ml, combining this method with others to get a better effect [4], [13], [21], [10].

In this phase it is important to be induced as soon as this has the greatest amplitude values of the tracking condition of the patient, such as ventilation, hydration and the presence of electrolytes. It should also be carried out induction in order to reduce the length of the incidence of shivering. To reduce side effects should be used with the fast pace of induction.

Phase maintain hypothermia

During backup should be very carefully monitor the patient's hemodynamic and biochemical. The most important is body temperature, which can vary by only 0.2 ° C - 0.5°C. Please note the air temperature in at least two places (eg. Bladder, and esophagus). It is still important to prevent dreszczom using deep sedation and relaxation [12].

In phase should maintain glycemic control, water - electrolyte. All the time you need to evaluate the parameters of homeostasis, renal and arterial blood gases. Also very important is prevention ArjoHuntleigh. If using a non-invasive techniques should be every 2 hours check the condition of the skin of the patient to rule out the occurrence of frostbite [13], [10].

Hold phase consists essentially entirely on the patient to monitor the parameters of the application of therapeutic hypothermia were normal.

During this phase must prevent unwanted actions:

- Chills - because they increase metabolism and heat production. In order to prevent shivers used relaxation and sedation. You can also be administered at a dose of magnesium sulfate 1-2 g / h.
- Arrhythmias - by lowering the body temperature decreases heart rate and bradycardia occurs. Also increases the risk of ventricular fibrillation.
- Polyuria - should increase fluid intake, because an increased diuresis. It should be constantly monitor the levels of electrolytes such as potassium, magnesium, calcium, phosphorus.
- Hyperglycemia - usually during therapy should be used insulin infusion because it is reduced insulin sensitivity. Blood glucose levels must be <10 mmol / l [15].

Phase heating body

This phase is the greatest threat to the patient. The main principle of this process is a slow heating (0.25 - 0.5°C / min). Heating can be started only after 48 hours from the start of cooling [11], [17].

Heat is applied until the temperature of the patient is was 36 ° C. All the time the patient is undergoing sedation and muscle relaxation. It is important that the patient be given large quantities of fluids, as the patient reaches hypotension due to vasodilatation in the heating process [10].

Complications of therapeutic hypothermia

Hypothermia is a non-physiological process for the patient, depending on the reduction of body temperature may be problems. Therefore, the therapeutic hypothermia therapy, if possible, they should be fought. Always remember that no matter what technique we use cooling, low temperature can cause many side effects.

Consequences of hypothermia

- the release of excess histamine (swelling of the eyelids, diffuse erythema, edema of the larynx)
- swallowing disorders
- stomach pain
- diarrhea
- vomiting [10].

Discussion

Despite the fact that we have a twenty-first century and medicine is already very developed, constantly creating new treatment techniques and equipment, some of which are able to replace many a good doctor, unfortunately, we can not say today that we can completely cure the effects of a sudden stop circulation.

In the event of a sudden cardiac arrest outside hospitals is the most important time. Every minute counts, and even the second, which is extremely valuable. It is important to perform CPR as soon as possible, and then make the appropriate treatment.

With scientific reports indicate that the most promising mechanism of cardiac arrest is ventricular fibrillation, in all studies, you will notice a big advantage survival of patients whose mechanism was ventricular fibrillation. Generally rhythms defibrillation have a better prognosis, so the ventricular tachycardia gives you a better chance of survival than, for example asystole, at which does not perform defibrillation.

It is extremely important that the patient survival was like the longest.

The study can be seen that patients who experienced sudden cardiac arrest die in the first days despite successful resuscitation. Therefore, treatment should be hypothermia, which increases the chances of patient survival. In the "Mild therapeutic hypothermia to improve the Neurologic come out after cardiac arrest" proved that therapeutic hypothermia gives high chances of survival long-term. The study was so accurate that the conclusions were published after 6 months after completion of therapy patients, all the time the patients were under the control clinics.

Scientists and physicians should consider the use hypothermia on pregnant woman with cardiac arrest. It is quite a controversial issue because of the views and ethical values. Although this study confirmed the efficacy of therapy in pregnant and the fact that it did not affect the fetus or to the development of pregnancy.

It is important to gather all data of patients that received the post-resuscitation hypothermia. Therefore, you should use the special therapy protocols, which collect information on the characteristics of patients, used cooling methods, pharmacotherapy as well as throughout the course of the phases of hypothermia treatment.

Therapeutic hypothermia should develop all the time, this method is highly promising for the future. With it you can save a lot of people who for various reasons, sudden cardiac arrest. Not only well performed CPR gives us the certainty of survival. You should fight for the good of the patient even after a hospital stay. With therapeutic hypothermia can affect the lives of patients without neurological damage, which is extremely important in life

Summary

1. Hypothermia works more effectively on the neurological condition of the patient after cardiac arrest compared with normothermic.
2. Ventricular fibrillation is the most promising mechanism of cardiac arrest in the use of therapeutic hypothermia.
3. The use of therapeutic hypothermia gives you a better chance of long-term survival after a cardiac arrest.
4. The use of therapeutic hypothermia in pregnant women results in a good clinical effect, while having no negative impact on the fetus and pregnancy.
5. Application of therapeutic hypothermia protocol allows the collection of patients whose treatment was carried out simultaneously, which is this fact related, the development of treatment methods.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.